

EVIDENCE REPORT

In Response to the UN Call for Input: Report of the UN Special Rapporteur on the situation of human rights in Belarus to the 81st Session of the UN General Assembly (UNGA 81) on 8–22 September 2026

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About RESIST Project

The RESIST Project is an EU-funded research consortium (EU grant ID: 101060749) that explored the impact of the so-called ‘anti-gender’ politics on democracies in Europe in the context of populist & illiberal politics (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060749>).

‘Anti-gender’ politics pose a threat to modern democracies because they challenge people’s everyday survival, bodily integrity, and self-determination. ‘Anti-gender’ spans the political spectrum and manifests not only in illiberal and authoritarian regimes, but also in democracies that are considered liberal and inclusive. Taking a transnational and intersectional approach, the RESIST Project has analysed ‘anti-gender’ formations across various European contexts and has evidenced the effects and impacts on the everyday lives of those vulnerable to it, and on democracies overall.

Summary

Since the 2020 presidential elections, repressions in Belarus have taken on a distinctly gendered character, disproportionately affecting women and LGBTIQ+ activists. The RESIST Project's case study on Belarus ([Filep 2024](#)) shows that these **'anti-gender' (i.e. anti-feminist, anti-LGBTIQ+) hostilities in Belarus are overwhelmingly state-driven and embedded within a broader authoritarian framework of repression**. The Belarusian state, supported by conservative religious institutions and allied civic groups, uses discriminatory laws, hostile rhetoric, and coercive practices to suppress dissent, legitimise violence, and stigmatise gender and sexual diversity.

The findings from the RESIST Project (2022-2026) demonstrate severe impacts of 'anti-gender' politics across all areas of life, including policing, healthcare, education, media, civil society, and family life ([RESIST Project Team 2024](#), [Kiening et al. 2024](#)). **Participants from Belarus – most of whom are now in exile – reported fear of arrest, torture, loss of child custody, cyber-harassment, and social isolation** ([Filep 2024](#)). The government's use of vague legal provisions to penalise feminist, LGBTIQ+ activism, and human rights organisations, coupled with state and societal hostility, has forced many activists, human rights defenders and queer individuals to leave the country ([Filep 2024](#)).

RESIST findings suggest that **displaced Belarusians continue to face gender-based hostility and SOGIESC-related discrimination throughout their migration journeys**. While crossing into Poland, some encountered anti-abortion protests and messaging, which intensified the trauma of fleeing and highlighted how humanitarian routes can still expose displaced people to gender-hostile environments ([Filep 2024](#)). Upon relocating to smaller European towns, several participants noted that gender non-conforming appearance or expression still prompted discriminatory reactions. This challenged their expectations of Europe as a space of gender equality and safety for LGBTIQ+ people ([Filep 2024](#)).

Despite these difficulties, migration also created new opportunities for safety and rights. In Poland and Western Europe, participants felt more able to live openly as LGBTIQ+ individuals, access rights-based mechanisms such as filing legal complaints, and begin building lives free from state repression. However, their **protection remained precarious: lacking passports, residency, or citizenship left them in vulnerable legal situations, illustrating a common humanitarian challenge where displaced LGBTIQ+ people face layered insecurities** ([Filep 2024](#)).

Many arrived without existing social networks, which intensified isolation. Some reported that **discrimination in Europe was often tied more to their Belarusian nationality** – with stereotypes linking Belarusians to “aggressor” Russia – than to their sexual orientation or gender identity. These experiences complicated their expectations of a “free” Europe and demonstrate how **xenophobia intersects with gender and LGBTIQ+ identities**, creating additional barriers to safety and belonging ([Filep 2024](#)).

Despite these challenges, activists remain resilient and determined to continue their resistance. Effective strategies include building networks with regions sharing similar political contexts, such as Central Asia and the Western Balkans, and leveraging social media to change public perceptions. Participants strongly emphasised the importance of solidarity, mutual support, and psychological care to sustain their activism and counteract the pervasive 'anti-gender' rhetoric ([Filep 2024](#)).

Key Takeaways

1. **'Anti-gender' politics in Belarus are state-led:** Participants overwhelmingly associate hostility against women, feminists, and LGBTIQ+ persons and activists with the state, viewing it as part of a broader machinery of political repression.
2. **Discrimination permeates everyday life beyond formal politics:** Gender and sexual hostilities are experienced in healthcare, education, workplaces, media, and even within pro-democracy and diaspora circles, not only through state actors.
3. **Fear of repression is pervasive and gendered:** Women and LGBTIQ+ people face heightened risks of arrest, imprisonment, torture, and child removal, producing a widespread climate of fear and self-censorship.
4. **Extreme anonymity has become a survival strategy:** Activists increasingly rely on invisibility and isolation to stay safe, which undermines collective organising and weakens community-based care structures.
5. **Severe forms of violence are normalised:** Participants reported experiences of detention, torture, forced labour, and gender-based humiliation, alongside routine exposure to sexist and homophobic media narratives.
6. **Cyber-harassment is organised and systematic:** Coordinated smear campaigns, doxxing, and online threats against feminist and queer activists are widespread and appear to involve organised, well-resourced actors.
7. **Forced migration is both an outcome and a form of resistance:** Leaving Belarus is often necessary for survival; at the same time, exile enables activists to continue advocacy, document abuses, and live more openly.
8. **Exile produces new vulnerabilities:** Displacement brings financial insecurity, legal precarity, isolation, and nationality-based discrimination, complicating activists' capacity to sustain their work.
9. **Transnational networks are central to resistance:** Belarusian queer and feminist activists rely heavily on regional and international alliances, particularly with contexts facing similar authoritarian conditions.
10. **Mutual care and support are essential but under-resourced:** Psychological care, legal assistance, and peer support are repeatedly identified as critical to sustaining long-term resistance but remain difficult to fund and institutionalise.

Recommendations

1. **Recognise ‘anti-gender’ mobilisations as a systemic threat:** ‘Anti-gender’ mobilisations should be recognised as a component of illiberal backsliding, border violence, and disinformation that poses a direct threat to basic human rights in Belarus. International actors should explicitly link gender and LGBTIQ+ repression in Belarus to broader rule-of-law and human rights conditionality frameworks.
2. **Strengthen international protection mechanisms for Belarussian human rights advocates:** Expand emergency visas, relocation programmes, and long-term legal pathways for Belarussian feminists and LGBTIQ+ activists at risk.
3. **Prioritise sustainable funding for exile-based, Belarussian human rights activism:** Donors should support core costs, mental health services, legal aid, and network coordination, not only short-term project funding.
4. **Recognise and address the intersectional vulnerabilities faced by LGBTIQ+ migrants, who often navigate multiple and compounding risks:** Adopt holistic support models that provide legal aid, psychosocial support, safe housing, and community-building opportunities.
5. **Embed intersectional analysis in all humanitarian planning, needs assessments, and protection mandates:** Ensure meaningful participation of migrant, racialised, lesbian, trans, intersex, disabled, and youth voices in strategy design, implementation, and monitoring.
6. **Recognise and strengthen community-driven networks as humanitarian infrastructure:** Support these Belarussian networks with micro-grants and cross-border collaboration platforms. Formally acknowledge informal Belarussian networks as critical actors in human rights (incl. LGBTIQ+) protection and integrate their knowledge into policy consultations and needs assessments.
7. **Support secure digital infrastructure and cyber-security training:** Given the prevalence of online harassment and surveillance, Belarussian activists need access to secure communication tools and digital protection resources.
8. **Counter anti-gender, anti-immigration and hate speech narratives in European countries that frame Belarussian exiles (incl. LGBTIQ+ people) – as threats:** Promote evidence-based public communication, support civil society organisations collaborating with Belarussian groups, challenge misinformation, and implement national and cross-national actions against hate speech that explicitly or implicitly targets LGBTIQ+ people and migrants.

Explanation & Evidence

The RESIST Project's case study on Belarus is based on expert interviews, biographical interviews and focus groups with participants, most of whom lives in exile. Methodological notes on the participants' demographic details and detailed discussion of all key findings is in the report:

Filep, E. (2024). *The RESIST Project Report. Effects of, and Resistances to 'Anti-Gender' Mobilisations Across Europe: A Report on Belarus.* RESIST Project.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13135722>

In general, participants in the RESIST's Belarusian case study described **pervasive gendered hostilities driven by state leaders, the Church, and state-controlled media, which legitimise discrimination and contribute to societal violence against women and LGBTIQ+ people.** Media were identified as a key propagator of hostility, with participants highlighting the routine circulation of unmoderated sexist, homophobic, and transphobic narratives and the reinforcement of women's reproductive roles. One participant described this environment as "giving a green light to societal aggression" ([Filep 2024](#)).

Human rights defenders, lawyers, and NGO workers reported heightened risks when defending abortion or LGBTIQ+ rights, frequently **facing accusations of "propaganda" or vaguely defined "extremist" activities.** Public denunciation through state media was described as particularly damaging, abruptly ending advocacy careers and creating a chilling effect that deters others from engaging in gender-equality work. One participant shared that her career in women's rights advocacy ended abruptly after being publicly accused of spreading propaganda, relating to a short educational video about queer rights. This accusation, featured on national television, overshadowed years of work. She said in her experience such accusations instil fear in potential allies, deterring them from engaging in support and solidarity ([Filep 2024](#)).

Participants who experienced detention for peaceful protest reported severe human rights violations, including gender-based intimidation, torture, forced labour, denial of medical care, and inhumane detention conditions. One person recounted being confined in overcrowded, smoke-filled rooms with poor sanitation, enforced (prolonged) sitting on hard surfaces, and punitive video surveillance. She was subjected to psychological and physical violence in prison, forced to work in unsafe conditions at a sewing factory with high disease transmission risks. Needles used for sewing were not sterilised, and basic hygiene was nearly impossible with limited access to sinks, toilets, and showers. Medical care was denied, and she was forced to work despite illness, leading to physical and psychological trauma ([Filep 2024](#)).

These experiences illustrate the use of gendered violence and criminalisation as tools of repression against women, feminists, LGBTIQ+ persons and activists.